

THE EOQ-FAS MODEL: A FUZZY ANT SYSTEM FOR DETERMINING ECONOMIC ORDER QUANTITY

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Abstract

This paper presents the application of an Ant System designed to facilitate decision making in stock management, specifically, the determination of economic order quantity under conditions of uncertainty and non-linearity. Thereafter, its validity and applicability is tested through a sample practical experiment.

Key words - Soft Computing Applications, Heuristic bio-inspired Ant Systems, Inventory Analysis, Economic Order Quantity, Design of IS.

I. INTRODUCTION

The environment faced by organizations in recent years has been characterized by constant change. It is a very long way indeed from being linear, gaussian, and stable, so that it would be difficult to believe it likely that decisions taken on the basis of past behaviour could lead to accurate future results. In the light of the uncertainty and complexity typical of this environment, the question arises of the need to seek out new approaches to deal with it.

In this respect, the main aim of the present paper is its interest in applying a biologically-inspired heuristic to stock control. This is one of the most vital aspects in managing any enterprise or economic unit, and might be summed up, among other features, as ensuring both good customer service and efficient production while keeping inventories as low as possible. The reason lies in the high costs associated with maintaining stocks; companies cannot carry the burden of large amounts of capital tied up in excessive holdings. Having stocks in store means having money lying idle, and to reduce this to a minimum, companies must attempt to bring about a coincidence in the opportunities offered by supply and demand, so that stocks reach the warehouse "just in time" for when they are required by customers.

Hence, the next section will carry out an analysis of the objectives and costs linked to inventory management. The following, third, section will be given over to a presentation of the Economic Order Quantity (EOQ) model, one of the principal tools developed in this area. It nevertheless has serious limitations, covered in the fourth section, related to its application in situations where the information available is vague or uncertain, forcing the problem to be approached using fuzzy numbers. With the object of overcoming these disadvantages, the fifth section presents the EOQ-FAS model, which involves the application of a heuristic based on nature, an Ant System model, as a methodology for optimization inspired by natural ant colonies, to solve the problem of determining the EOQ. The validity of this is corroborated by an example of practical experimentation included in the sixth section. The paper ends with a number of conclusions about the development of the research, laying out several lines for future work that can be glimpsed from the potential usefulness of this tool in designing other intelligent information systems for taking management decisions.

II. OBJECTIVES AND COSTS OF INVENTORY MANAGEMENT

Productive processes require the supply of items necessary for obtaining the outputs which are the ultimate object of the firm's activity. Hence there is a need to consider the problem of providing these items to the centres of production, in view of how important they are in determining the efficiency of the activity of a company. After all, supply can be guaranteed only when the firm has materials and other items at the given moment when they are required.

It is obvious that firms wish to maximize their profits, and this can be attained by achieving two fundamental items: maximization of customer service and minimization of operating costs.

In the strict sense, customer service is the ability of a company to satisfy the needs of its clients. In stock control, this term is used to describe the availability of products an enterprise owns when they are needed, serving as a measure of the effectiveness of inventory management. If it is kept in mind that in this sense the customer may be a purchaser, a distributor, another plant in the organization, or the work station where the next operation in the production process will take place, the concept of customer service is generalized, expanded and rounded out.

There are various alternative ways of measuring this service, each with its strengths and weaknesses. Among those most often used would be the percentage of orders shipped, the percentage of product lines transported and the number of days orders are held up for lack of stocks, to name but three.

It should be noted that stock inventories help maximize customer service by protecting an enterprise against uncertain events. Thus, if it were possible to foresee exactly what quantity of materials will be required by customers and when, error-free demand planning would be feasible. However, demand and delivery times for supply of a given material are uncertain in many cases, and might arouse dissatisfaction among customers relating to their needs for service. Consequently, it may be necessary to hold extra inventory (safety stock) as a shield against unpredictable situations.

In relation to efficiency of operations, stocks held can assist in making manufacturing operations more effective in four different ways:

1. Stocks permit operations to go on with differing production rhythms and processing of them to be carried out separately and in the most economical fashion possible. If two or more operations in a sequence have different rates of output, and must be processed efficiently, this objective may be attained by introducing a buffer stock between them.
2. Stocks can balance production; the building up of inventory in advance for sale in periods of irregular demand may permit reductions in overtime, training, subcontracting or capacity. Through this levelling out of production, manufacturing can steadily produce quantities matching a varying demand. The advantage of this strategy is that the costs of changes in the levels of production are avoided.
3. Inventory permits manufacture in large production batches, leading to the following benefits:
 - Lower set-up costs for a given product. The cost of manufacturing a batch or series is dependent upon both setting-up expenses and the costs for the series. Setting-up costs are fixed, but batch costs vary as a function of the number of units produced. Thus, if manufacture is in large batches, the initial costs are absorbed by a great number of units, with the unit cost lower.
 - An increase in production capacity brings with it a growth in the production resources used, but reduces the percentage of time spent setting up, since time in a workplace is used both on setting up and on the processing proper. However, products are obtained solely during the process time and not during preparation time. Thus, if production series

are large in size, setting-up time diminishes and there is more time available for obtaining units of output. This is especially important when the resources needed are “bottle-necks”, because the time used in the initial preparation of these resources is wasted, and so capacity is lost.

4. Stocks allow a production process to buy in large quantities, and this brings about both lower emission costs per unit, and the concession of volume discounts.

Nevertheless, even if it might seem that holding stocks brings only advantages, getting these requires a financial effort or sacrifice. The problem lies in balancing investment in stocks with:

- *Customer service.* The bigger the volume of stocks, the greater the customer service, as they will never have to wait for goods or face the dissatisfactions of not having their order fulfilled.
- *Costs associated with changing levels of production.* If these are allowed to float with demand in an attempt to seek minimization of stocks, the result can be excess capacity in equipment, time overruns, high training costs and outlays on setting up the machines.
- *Cost of ordering goods.* Low levels of stock holdings may be managed with less effort, but conversely involve considerable increases in the cost of handling orders.
- *Transport costs.* Transporting products in small quantities gives a higher unit cost than with large amounts. Nevertheless, large orders imply big holdings of inventory.

If stocks are held, things must be so arranged that the benefits obtained from them are greater than the costs that must be borne. On this point, it should be noted that traditionally [López-Díaz y Menéndez-Menéndez, 1989] the decision-making related to inventory management took into account the following costs:

1. *Purchase cost of the articles.* This cost represents the amount paid out when acquiring an article purchased and is composed of the cost of the material and any other direct cost needed in order for the material in question to be present within the firm.
2. *Holding or warehousing costs.* These costs refer to outlays incurred by the enterprise and are proportionate to the stock volume held in its stores. Thus, as inventories grow, so do costs of this type.
3. *Costs of processing an order for goods.* These ordering costs are related to the firm and to the supplier. The cost of sending off an order does not depend solely on the quantity ordered, since there are some costs which are independent of quantity. These can be reduced by ordering in large amounts, so that the number of orders put in is smaller. However, this will lead to higher inventory levels, and in turn to greater holding or warehousing costs for the articles.
4. *Out-of-stock costs.* If demand exceeds forecast, items will go out of stock, that is, there will be insufficient articles available to satisfy customer demand or demands from the production process. The costs arising from this situation can sometimes be high and would include: the costs of lost sales, of returning order documents, of losing clients, and the like. Such breaks in availability can be avoided by maintaining extra stocks to protect the enterprise against situations in which real demand is greater than forecast. Nevertheless, such a practice brings with it higher holding costs for the articles stored.
5. *Costs associated with capacity.* When the volume of capacity varies because of changing needs higher than planned, then hire, training, overtime, stoppage, and other costs are incurred. This type of cost can be avoided by levelling out production, so as to manufacture products in periods of low demand that can be sold at times when demand rises. Once again, this has the downside of causing an increase in holding costs.

in. ECONOMIC ORDER QUANTITY MODEL

As pointed out above, the objectives of inventory management are to supply the required customer service level while reducing the total amount of all the costs involved. To attain these twin objectives, two basic questions must be answered [Curwin and Slater, 1996]: "How much should be ordered each time?" and "When should an order be put in?".

In relation to these, the Economic Order Quantity Model (EOQ) is a mathematical representation of the costs involved in managing stocks, and despite its simplicity, it has provided reasonable solutions for a great number of practical problems. What derives from this model is founded on five starting hypotheses of a restrictive nature [Harris, 1915]:

1. Demand is constant and known.
2. Delivery delay is nil, that is, there is no gap between lodging an order and receiving the articles.
3. Articles are produced or bought in batches and not continuously.
4. Ordering and holding costs are known and constant over time.
5. Articles all arrive simultaneously.

The EOQ model has developed on the supposition that there are only two sorts of cost associated with stock management: the cost of lodging an order, or ordering cost, and the cost of holding materials in store. These assumptions are valid when it is a matter of finished products, demand for which is independent and fairly uniform. However, there are numerous situations in which the EOQ model's assumptions are not fulfilled.

In the cases which do match, the costs of lodging an order will be incurred whenever an order is sent to the suppliers and will generally include administrative work, telephone calls, postage, journeys, and similar, or some combination of these. In their turn, the costs of holding materials in store will be made up of the cost of warehouse staff in charge of handling them, insurance, taxes, depreciation, deterioration, obsolescence, and so forth.

In this way, for the purposes of mathematical representation, if the quantity ordered each time is denoted by Q and the constant annual demand is termed D , a year being considered the period to be analyzed, then the level of stock as a function of time will be as shown in Figure 1. If the initial order were for Q , since there is no delay between ordering and reception of materials, then automatically there would be Q in the warehouse. Moreover, since demand is constant over time, that is, D units per year, the time needed for the order to be completely used up would be Q/D years and the number of orders per year D/Q .

Thus, for a processing cost per order lodged of C_o , the yearly cost of ordering would be:

$$\text{Yearly Cost of Ordering} = C_o \times \frac{D}{Q}$$

and for a unit cost of holding materials in store of C_m , the annual warehousing cost would be:

$$\text{Annual Warehousing Cost} = C_m \times \frac{Q}{2}$$

because with orders of equal size and with demand constant, the amount in store on average would be $Q/2$.

Further, to calculate the yearly cost of supply of a material it would be necessary to take into account the purchase cost of C_p , which is the amount of money spent on one unit of the material. As a first approximation, this would be considered constant over time and independent of the volume acquired. Thus, the total annual cost would be provided by the following equation:

$$\text{Total Annual Cost (TAC)} = C_p \times \frac{D}{Q} + C_m \times \frac{Q}{2} + C_c \times D$$

and a graphic representation of it as a function of the quantity ordered would be as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

If the intention is to calculate the quantity to be ordered so as to minimize the total cost of stock in accordance with the starting hypothesis, the equation for total costs is derived with respect to the quantity Q so as to obtain the optimal point or points for the function:

$$\frac{d}{dQ} = -C_0 \times \frac{1}{Q^2} + \frac{C_{ua}}{2Q}$$

with the derivation equal to 0 the outcome is that:

$$-C_0 \times \frac{1}{Q^2} + \frac{C_{ua}}{2Q} = 0$$

and stripping out Q the result is:

$$\frac{C_{ua}}{2} = Q \times \frac{1}{Q^2} \quad \therefore Q = \pm \sqrt{\frac{2C_0 D}{C_{ua}}}$$

To distinguish between a maximum and a minimum, the equation for total stock costs is re-derived yielding. For it to be a minimum, the second derivation must be positive and in this case, it would be positive when Q is positive, so that it may be concluded that the minimum would be:

$$\frac{d^2 TAC}{dQ^2} = \frac{2C_0 D}{Q^3} \quad Q = \sqrt{\frac{2C_0 D}{C_{ua}}}$$

IV. THE EOQ MODEL IN CONDITIONS OF UNCERTAINTY AND NON-LINEARITY

The traditional approach based on the hypotheses of this model is very restrictive and does not match the realities of the current business world. Hence, criticisms that may be made of it correspond to some of the assumptions it requires to be made:

1. *Demand is not always known*, that is, only imprecise information about its behaviour may be available. Thus, a better representation of demand might be achieved through the use of fuzzy numbers [Kaufmann and Gil-Aluja, 1986].
2. *The costs of lodging an order and of storing articles in the warehouse are not always known and constant over time*. As occurs with demand, an estimate of their future behaviour is being made. To this end, it is suggested that it may be of more interest to represent them as fuzzy numbers rather than as precise estimates. Additionally, their behaviour need not be linear, so that the costs function is not necessarily derivable, an essential condition for applying the traditional model.
3. *Other different costs may arise apart from those of ordering and storing*. In real life, enterprises incur many other costs, such as those caused by being out of stock, depreciation of materials, and so forth, which complicate analysis using the traditional model.

On the basis of these criticisms, the present paper attempts to formulate an approach to the problem of calculating the economic quantity that goes beyond the traditional model, so that it would operate even in conditions of uncertainty and non-linearity.

For this purpose, it should first be accepted that demand may not be known in a precise way. Thus, it may be of interest to represent it as a trapezoidal fuzzy number (TFN). In this manner, it is possible to cover not only those situations in which its behaviour is known with certainty, but also others, in which it is possible to estimate certain values within which it will be found.

In addition, the costs incurred by an enterprise for storing materials as an inventory to meet requirements of a production process are:

- *The cost of articles or their net purchase price.* The behaviour of this need not be linear, that is, the most usual state of affairs is for a supplier firm to grant discounts for volume purchase. Moreover, to be able to cover all possible situations, it would be advisable to represent them as fuzzy numbers, with TFN being suggested.

So, if the supplier establishes n sales prices for given articles between the maximum and minimum orders, according to the volume ordered, a representation of them might be:

$$cd = \{ca, \tilde{ca}_1, ca_n\}$$

and the respective ranges of order size delimiting them:

$$* = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_j\}$$

- *Holding or warehousing costs.* These costs may have a non-linear behaviour, so that their form and characteristic values need to be identified. In any case, as they are estimates they may best be represent by TFN: $\tilde{cp} = \{cp, \tilde{cp}_2, \dots, \tilde{cp}_r\}$

- *The costs of lodging an order.* These costs too are not necessarily linear in their behaviour, for example, the transport element, and so their values may be set using TFN.

$$c7 = \{cA, \tilde{cZ}_1, \dots, \dots, cJ\}$$

- *Depreciation costs.* Such costs are not considered in the traditional model, arising fundamentally in respect of articles which are perishable or subject to fashion trends. They are not normally precisely known, so that handling them in the form of TFN may allow better representation of them: $\tilde{cd} = \{^d, \tilde{cd}_2, \dots, \tilde{cd}_l\}$

This approach intends to give a view of the problem with a wider scope and thus cover day-to-day situations faced by businesses. Nevertheless, one hypothesis from the traditional model is retained: a uniform distribution of demand over the period under study, even if its value is imprecise. Furthermore, the focus suggested does not permit a simple resolution, because the function for total costs is very complex. So, with the aim of finding an order quantity minimizing the costs incurred the suggestion is the use of a heuristic based on nature: an Ant System. In this way, through its application, while the solution reached may not be the optimal value, it will be very close to it.

V. DESIGN OF A FUZZY ANT SYSTEM AS A SUPPORT FOR THE EOQ MODEL

The determining of the EOQ described in the sections above has traditionally been resolved using linear optimization methods, which cease to offer a true solution if that intends to take into consideration the possible behaviours of the various types of costs involved.

For that reason, this section looks at the designing of an Ant System to solve the problem of forecasting the quantities to be ordered for a given period under analysis, in such a way as to overcome the principal restrictions of the traditional methodology.

The basic functioning of an Ant System (AS) is as follows (Figure 3): in each iteration, a population of H ants progressively establishes, in accordance with a state transition rule dependent on the information to hand, differing routes across the graph (solutions to the problem). Once these have been evaluated, the arcs associated with the most promising solutions are reinforced with an additional dose of pheromone, while the pheromone contained in the other arcs in the graph is deemed to evaporate.

Fig. 3

In addition, it should be pointed out that the development of the AS implemented uses information expressed in the form of trapezoidal fuzzy numbers.

A. Generation of solutions

For the resolution of the problem under study it must first be determined what route options lie open to each agent with a view to providing a feasible solution. For this purpose, consideration must be given to the limits set on the enterprise when lodging orders, these normally being fixed by the size of the minimum order a supplier will deliver, the capacity of storage space available, the prices offered for different volumes of order, and other features. [López-González and Rodríguez-Fernández, 1995; López-González et al., 1998b]. The influence of such variables on the function representing the Total Inventory Cost (TIC) leads this function not to be linear, so that when it comes to considering the inventory cost each of the sections originating from the influence of these variables must be taken into account.

In this way, each section of the TIC function is considered as a node in the journey to be made by each agent, which will establish the solution brought by each ant. Thus, application of the state transition rule used by ant systems (a proportional-random rule), it is possible to work out the probability that an ant standing in a given section will choose to move to another section, this being obtained from the following expression:

$$pt(a, r) = \begin{cases} \frac{[r(r, j)]^a \cdot [7(r, s)]^b}{\sum_{j \in J_k(r)} [r(r, j)]^a \cdot [7(r, s)]^b} & \text{if } r \in J_k(r) \\ \frac{E[r(r, w)]^a \cdot [7(r, w)]^b}{\sum_{w \in J_k(r)} [r(r, w)]^a \cdot [7(r, w)]^b} & \text{otherwise} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where r is the pheromone level of the arc, q is the cost of the arc, $J_k(r)$ is the set of nodes reachable from r not yet visited by ant k and a and b are parameters establishing a balance between the relative importance of memory-based and heuristic information.

B. Evaluation of solutions

The suitability of each route can be determined by calculating the total inventory cost represented by that solution. This is given by the sum of the costs established for this purpose, which, in accordance with the points raised above, are the following:

- **Acquisition cost.** As a first step, it is necessary to determine the time taken by a supplier to provide the quantity to be ordered which represents the solution, so that this purchase cost can be calculated by multiplying the fuzzy demand by the fuzzy cost of supply within this interval.
- **Holding cost.** This is based on the average stock held, and grows with the size of the order lodged. In this way the average stock is obtained by averaging the quantity, assuming demand stays stable. On the basis of this and as a function of the type of approximation that the behaviour of holding costs matches, it is possible to calculate the total outlay on them.
- **Ordering costs.** This sort of cost increases with the number of orders lodged, so that the smaller the amount ordered, the greater the number of times that contact will have to be made with the supplier. Further, the number of orders depends on demand. As this is imprecise, there will have to be a fuzzy division [Dubois and Prade, 1980] of this demand by the quantity to be ordered established by each solution, so as to work out the number of separate orders that will have to be made. From the results obtained and as a function of the type of approximation that ordering costs fit, their total amount can be calculated.
- **Depreciation costs.** The amount of these costs rises with higher levels of average inventory, in other words, with larger order volume, so that once the average stock has been determined, it is just a question of calculating what it will be as a function of their behaviour or an approximation to it.

With the information noted above, all of the components of the total cost for each solution are to hand, and adding them together will yield the Total Inventory Cost. In the operational model, this cost is approximated to its trapezoidal form [Dubois and Prade, 1980; Kaufmann and Gil-Aluja, 1986] with a view to simplifying calculations, even at the loss of some precision.

The solution will be provided by the amount that brings this total cost to its minimum, so that the option taken is to calculate fit as the inverse of cost, this being the fuzzy distance between the trapezoidal value previously calculated and the origin (singleton 0). In accordance with the previous procedure, this leads to the best solutions (the lowest total costs), having the best fit to the problem.

C. Pheromone update

With reference to the pheromone matrix, the initial pheromone levels are deemed equal for all sections. Thereafter, when each ant has generated its solution, a global pheromone update rule modifies the level of pheromone for each section in two ways, these being:

- Evaporation of pheromone from the arcs not visited by any ant in the current iteration (unpromising arcs).
- Addition of pheromone to those visited as a function of the goodness of the solution generated by the ant that visited them (promising arcs).

The expression for the global pheromone update rule is: $t(r,s) = (1-p) \cdot t(r,s) + \sum_k \tau_k(r,s)$

H
 $t = /$

where p is the parameter for pheromone evaporation and nt is the number of ants.

$$Jr^*(r,s) = \begin{cases} f(s) & \text{If then ant } k \text{ has visited } (r,s) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where $f(S_k)$ is a quantity of pheromone directly proportional to the goodness of the solution generated by ant k , $C(S_k)$.

VI. EXAMPLE OF A PRACTICAL EXPERIMENT

To check the working of the EOQ-FAS model, an operational model with an example of a practical illustration is developed below: Let there be a furniture factory that buys various types of wood for use in making its finished products, so that for one of them there is a specialized warehouse that can hold up to 6,000 tonnes of this wood.

According to forecast made, the demand for furniture using this type of wood over the period under consideration permits calculation of the amounts needed to supply the production process, and these are set as the fuzzy trapezoidal number: (5,000, 5,250, 5,500, 5,700).

The supplier for this sort of wood will not make deliveries of under 500 tonnes, and an estimate of the sale price policy this supplier will follow, according to order size, is shown in Table 1:

Size of order	Purchase Price
son. 1-500 Tm.	25 n/Tm.
1.001-2.000 Tm.	24 n/Tm.
2.001-3.000 Tm.	23 n/Tm.
3.001-4.000 Tm.	22 n/Tm.
4.001-5.000 Tm.	21 n/Tm.
5.001-6.000 Tm.	20 n/Tm.

Table 1

The cost of putting in an order behaves proportionately (Figure 4), so that every time an order is lodged an estimated transport cost is incurred of (7,500, 7,600, 7,650, 7,750).

For its part, holding costs behave in a semi-fixed way (Figure 5), since they relate to warehouse operatives handling goods in store.

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

The parameters determining them are those shown in Table 2, immediately below;

Parameter	Value
Cost of one staff member (κ*):	(50.000, 51.000, 51.000, 52.500)
Cost of two staff (ak₂):	(98.000, 100.000, 100.000, 105.000)
Cost of three staff (κ*):	(145.000, 148.000, 150.000, 155.000)
Capacity of one staff member (A):	2.500
Capacity of two staff (B):	5.000

Table 2

Finally, the depreciation suffered by a tonne of stored wood per day is estimated at (1.05; 1.1; 1.15; 1.17).

On the basis of the information given, the quantity that should be requested from the supplier so as to keep costs at a minimum during the period under consideration is to be calculated.

Application of the EOQ-FAS model to the search for the optimum order quantity developed by considering measures of fit for the solutions as indicated below:

A solution generated at random using the model might be to order 1,200 whenever stocks held are exhausted. The purchase costs for the demand if orders of this size were lodged would be:

$$C_{ci} = (24 \cdot 5000, 24 \cdot 5250, 24 \cdot 5500, 24 \cdot 5700) = (120000, 126000, 132000, 136800)$$

For its part, storage of the goods in the warehouse would require only one member of staff, as the average stock held is 600 tonnes, so that the holding cost would be:

$$C_p = (50000, 51000, 51000, 52000)$$

Ordering costs are proportionate to the number of orders sent in to cover the demand, hence here they would be:

$$C_7 = f. \left(7500 \frac{5000}{1200}, 7600 \cdot \frac{5250}{1200}, 7650 \frac{5500}{1200}, 7700 \frac{5700}{1200} \right) = (31250, 33250, 35662, 36812)$$

Finally, depreciation costs for an average stock of 600 tonnes would be:

$$C_d = (600^{1.05}, 600^{1.1}, 600^{1.15}, 600^{1.17}) = (826, 1157, 1560, 1780)$$

Addition of all the above costs would yield the total inventory cost if orders are made of 1200 tonnes each time, the inverse of the distance of this from the origin, giving the fit of the solution to the problem: *Total Cost* = (202076, 211407, 220222, 227392)

In applying the operational model, the parameters used to obtain the solution from the system proposed were a total of 20 iterations, with 50 ants and a pheromone evaporation rate equal to 0.1. In the specific case analyzed, the final solution obtained was the following:

A graphic representation of the best solution at each iteration is shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE LINES OF RESEARCH

This paper has presented a fuzzy ant system permitting determination of the optimum order quantity, with a practical experiment allowing a demonstration of its validity and usefulness. This suggests the opening up of a line of future work by its authors with the object of expanding and generalizing applications to other problems of quadratic allocation.

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